

Supplementary Table 1. Compilation of Pearson’s correlation coefficients (R) and p-values for correlation tests between whole-body and mass-specific metabolic rate, genus age (first appearance datum), and absolute median paleolatitude. Bivalves with larger body sizes and thus higher total calorific needs tend to have lower per gram calorific needs. Whole-body metabolic rate decreases, and mass-specific metabolic rate increases, with genus age. Both whole-body and mass-specific metabolic rates decrease with absolute paleolatitude. The data here are each post-Carboniferous genus that had all values calculated (n = 1111).

Pearson Correlation Coefficients, N = 1111				
	Whole-Body Metabolic Rate	Mass-Specific Metabolic Rate	Genus Age (FAD)	 Median Paleolatitude
Whole-Body Metabolic Rate	1.0000	R = -0.56 p < 0.0001	R = -0.079 p = 0.0081	R = -0.20 p < 0.0001
Mass-Specific Metabolic Rate	R = -0.56 p < 0.0001	1.0000	R = 0.15 p < 0.0001	R = -0.50 p < 0.0001
Genus Age (FAD)	R = -0.079 p = 0.00081	R = 0.15 p < 0.0001	1.0000	R = -0.17 p < 0.0001
 Median Paleolatitude 	R = -0.20 p < 0.0001	R = -0.50 p < 0.0001	R = -0.17 p < 0.0001	1.0000

Supplementary Table 2. Comparison of confidence intervals computed for relative hyperthermal vulnerability using 90% and 95% confidence intervals. Mean extinction risk during stages associated with hyperthermal onset for low-latitude bivalve genera with higher mass-specific metabolic rates is increased compared to baseline conditions, and this result is significant regardless of whether 90% or 95% confidence intervals are used.

	90% CI		95% CI	
	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
Whole-Body Metabolic Rate	-0.221	0.269	-0.25	0.329
Whole-Body Metabolic Rate (Tropical Genera)	-0.44	0.083	-0.506	0.131
Mass-Specific Metabolic Rate	-0.188	0.775	-0.274	0.855
Mass-Specific Metabolic Rate (Tropical Genera)	0.067	0.537	0.028	0.595

Supplementary Figure 1. Representation of bivalve orders in our dataset based on number of genera (n = 1111), separated by geological stage.

Supplementary Figure 2. Representation of bivalve orders in our dataset based on number of occurrences ($n = 138,419$), separated by geological stage.

Supplementary Figure 3. Regression coefficients from logistic regression analyses of extinction as a function of whole-body (above) and mass-specific (below) metabolic rate in bivalves, tropical genera only. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals. Stages associated with the onset (red) or continuation (orange) of hyperthermal conditions are colored. Data points whose error bars intersect the x-axis (statistically insignificant selectivity) are grayed out. Similar trends are observed as in Figure 3 for all bivalve genera: a higher whole-body metabolic rate is generally associated with a reduced risk of extinction, whereas a higher mass-specific metabolic rate generally associated with an increased risk of extinction, in the post-Paleozoic.

Supplementary Figure 4. Regression coefficients from logistic regression analyses of extinction as a function of whole-body (above) and mass-specific (below) metabolic rate in bivalves, polar genera only. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals. Stages associated with the onset (red) or continuation (orange) of hyperthermal conditions are colored. Data points whose error bars intersect the x-axis (statistically insignificant selectivity) are grayed out. Similar trends are observed as in Figure 3 for all bivalve genera: a higher whole-body metabolic rate is generally associated with a reduced risk of extinction, whereas a higher mass-specific metabolic rate

generally associated with an increased risk of extinction, in the post-Paleozoic, though the strength of this trend is potentially limited by undersampling of high-latitude bivalves in the fossil record.

Supplementary Figure 5. Relative hyperthermal vulnerability (RHV) of increasing whole-body and mass-specific metabolic rate in bivalves, showing any deviation of hyperthermal extinction selectivity (individual events in black and mean across all events in grey) from baseline selectivity (i.e., RHV = 0). A, whole-body metabolic rate. B, whole-body metabolic rate, high latitude genera only. C, mass-specific metabolic rate. D, mass-specific metabolic rate, high latitude genera only. Mean extinction risk for high latitude bivalves with respect to both whole-body and mass-specific metabolic rate is not significantly altered during stages associated with hyperthermal onset compared to baseline conditions.

Supplementary Figure 6. Regression coefficients from logistic regression analyses of origination as a function of whole-body (above) and mass-specific (below) metabolic rate in bivalves. Error bars indicate 90% confidence intervals. Stages associated with the onset (red) or continuation (orange) of hyperthermal conditions are colored. Data points whose error bars intersect the x-axis are grayed out. Because originations associated with hyperthermals will likely have a response and observation lag (e.g., Alroy 2008), such originations may appear pulsed in the following stages. From the mid-Jurassic onwards, mass-specific metabolic rate has

a positive relationship with origination. Compare with Figure 3 of the main text—both originations and extinctions are higher in bivalves with higher per-gram calorific demands.

Supplementary Figure 7. Counts of B_0 scaling constants sourced from Vladimirova et al. (2003), divided between heterodont and non-heterodont bivalves. From Brey (2010), we use B_0 constants of $7.87 \times 10^8 W g^{-3/4}$ for heterodont bivalves, and $7.31 \times 10^8 W g^{-3/4}$ for all other bivalves. We would expect heterodont bivalves to have correspondingly higher standard metabolism coefficients from Vladimirova et al. (2003) than do non-heterodont bivalves, however, we do not observe such a relationship.